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CO-CREATING SERVICE EXPERIENCE WITH STAKEHOLDERS: THE CASE OF TAIWAN'S CULTURAL CREATIVE INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

Recently, co-creation has become an important issue in service design. However, there is very limited research on exploring how a firm can efficiently and effectively co-create with different types of stakeholders to deliver a holistic service experience. To date, the cultural creative industry has been steadily popular around the world. Therefore, this study aimed to explore the ways in which a firm, Lin's Ceramics Studio (LCS), co-creates with different stakeholders to offer Chinese tea culture experiences in Taiwan's culture industry. In doing so, this study adopted an ethnographic approach to obtain deeper insights into how LCS can design and deliver service experiences, and to build a detailed description of the service design project. In this study, the researchers stayed in the field over seven months to collect data by participating observations and interviews with different stakeholders. The findings of the study highlight the need for research to investigate many of the above issues, and in particular, methods for improving co-creation with stakeholders for the cultural creative industry.

Keywords: service design, co-creation, cultural creative industries

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, service design schemes have been explored throughout the world. Service design refers to the design of an integrated, favorable, and unforgettable service experience (Bitner, Ostrom, & Morgan, 2008). More importantly, one of the core issues for service design is to put clients and stakeholders at the centre of design activities (Holmlid & Evenson, 2006) and to co-create with them. Although previous studies have concentrated

on the values of co-creation with the stakeholders, they are complicated by individual differences in the emerging roles of service delivery. While co-creation appears to take place within networks of relationships rather than in simple dyadic relationships (Prahalad & Ramaswamy, 2004), inevitably stakeholders' involvement and participation in the service design process bring more challenges. Dabholkar, Bobbitt, and Lee (2003) advocated that a firm often encounters several issues during the co-creation of service experience, including lack of stakeholders' individual thoughts about their experiences, lack of appropriate strategies for stakeholders' requirements, and fear of what the stakeholders experience may reveal. Therefore, more studies need to be conducted to ascertain the ways in which a firm can efficiently and effectively co-create with different types of stakeholders to deliver a holistic service experience. In 1997, "the creative economy" was officially launched in England. To date, the cultural creative industry has been growing steadily around the world (Matheson, 2006). Furthermore, Pratt (2008) pointed out that cultural creative industry is a combination of production and consumption or a mixture of manufacturing and services. Therefore, the cultural creative industry is a very wide scope with complex stakeholders. Therefore, this study presents a detailed case study of the cultural creative industry to explore how stakeholders co-create a unique service experience through service design process.

LITERATURE REVIEW

TAIWAN'S CULTURE AND CREATIVE INDUSTRY

Matheson (2006) asserted that the term "creative industry" was initially used to explain 'design, advertising, film, fashion, interactive technologies,

popular music, and a host of other professions.' Nowadays, the cultural creative industry is increasingly recognized as one of the powerful engines driving economic growth in many countries (Fesel & Söndermann, 2007). In fact, the cultural creative industry spans a variety of economic sectors, including manufacturing, service and marketing branches (Fesel & Söndermann, 2007). Due to historical and geographical factors, there are various cultures in Taiwan, such as Chinese traditional culture, indigenous culture and western culture. As time went on, a unique cultural characteristic took shape in Taiwan. Based on these rich cultural characteristics, Taiwan's cultural creative industry is expanding, such as bamboo stool "BAMBOOL" and "43" of the fashionable craft brand "yii" (as shown in Figure 1).

Figure 1. bamboo stool "BAMBOOL" and "43".
<http://www.yiidesign.com/ch/collection.php>,
<http://www.konstantin-grcic.com/project/43/>

SERVICE EXPERIENCE

Gentile, Spiller, and Noci (2007) defined experience as "originated from a set of interactions between a customer and a product, a company, or part of its organization, which provoke a reaction." Otto and Ritchie (1996) claimed that the service experience is the participants' subjective and mental response. Customers can obtain service experiences through different touchpoints. Actually, touchpoints are not only the main basis for overall service experience, they also play an important role in the integration of service experience (Zeithaml, Pasuraman, & Berry, 1990). Therefore, the service experience is a strictly personal perception of services which originates from the five senses coming into contact with touchpoints; In addition, the production of service experience must be experienced personally and cannot be transmitted by word of mouth.

Grace and O'Cass (2004) asserted that service experience consists of core services, employee service, and servicescapes (e.g., physical evidence). First, the "core services" could be treated as the basic content for being in business (Gronroos, 1990). For example, the retail store offers commodities to customers. Secondly, "employee service" refers to the salesclerks within the organization that provide service to customers, and the employees play an important part of the service, like a clerk in the bank. Thirdly, "servicescape" represents the consumption settings in a physical surrounding. Lovelock and Wirtz (2004) pointed out that servicescape is the style and appearance of the physical environment and the part of experience that is delivered to the customer. Furthermore, the servicescape not only provides tangible clues to evaluate the brand value, but also becomes an important factor to judge service experience after consumption (Bitner, 1992; Grace & O'Cass, 2004). It should be noted that this study conducted service experience construction (Grace & O'Cass, 2004) to investigate the service experience of Taiwan's cultural creative industry in detail. On the whole, service experience can play a crucial role in customer evaluation and satisfaction with services (Otto and Ritchie, 1996). However, the components of experience are mixed and intangible. Compared with tangible products, service is more difficult to create or measure (Zeithaml, 1988). A bad service experience could result in reduction of the number of customers and poor evaluation for the organization (Tseng, Qin Hai & Su, 1999). Therefore, more and more cases use services design methods to shape a unique service experience.

SERVICE DESIGN

Drawing the definition from Wikipedia (2010), service design is "a profession concerned with improving the experience that customers receive from a service provider." Moreover, service design can be treated as a feasible approach of designing for experience to reach people through different touchpoints over time (Servicedesign.org, 2008). In the past, discussion of service design with different viewpoints, such as service innovation, services marketing or service management, originated from a business perspective (Moritz, 2005), rather than from the customer side (Maffei, Mager, & Sangiorgi, 2005).

Recently, Holmlid and Evenson (2006) and Mager (2004) highlighted that service design is an outside-in viewpoint and human-oriented thinking. Design Council (2005) proposed four phases of the design process: *discover*, *define*, *develop* and *deliver*. First of all, in the *discover* phase, the service design team (hereafter SDT) conduct market research, interview, observation or data analysis to find out the requirements and expectations of customers and stakeholders and to establish deep empathy of different roles. Secondly, in the *define* phase, SDTs aim to verify the value of service innovation opportunities and gaps. They integrate and analyze the information collected from the *discover* phase to plan development strategies, and extract the point of view (POV) for service design. Third, in the *develop* phase, design teams do brainstorming, make prototypes, and get feedback to modify design concepts for service innovation opportunities and gaps. Finally, during the *deliver* phase, designers systematically evaluate and adjust new services; at last, they draw a new services blueprint for service delivery and implementation. Thus, this study adopted the 4Ds phases to analyze the co-creation of a new service experience in Taiwan's cultural creative industry.

CO-CREATION

Blomkvist, Holmlid, and Segelström (2010) have identified co-creation as one of the critical service design research trends. For the viewpoints of customers and stakeholders, Fullerton (2009) pointed out that co-creation means stakeholders from different backgrounds work together through an open process and give a holistic consideration of service contents. Simply stated, co-creation could be seen as a resource that can be managed and explored for service value. In the past, traditional development often use existing, professional or heavy users to create many reliable concepts, a co-creation process that invites more untypical users (unfocus group/ users) would be able to produce more original ideas or innovative concepts. Finally, the co-creation "has to do with the value-creation process and leads to value-in-use" in comparison to co-design (Lusch, Vargo, & O'Brien, 2007). Who should be involved in the co-creation of services? Campbell (2003) asserted the need to integrate the

knowledge and requirements of different customers in the co-creation process; therefore, it can be treated as one part of the customer-knowledge competence. However, customers are not the only participants in co-creation; the stakeholders of service provider network are also important participants. Co-creation describes collaboration with customers for innovative service and has become a hot item of service design (Lusch et al., 2007). In general, the participants should include all levels of the company, from key managers at senior levels to front-line employees (Fullerton, 2009). In addition, based on the case study from service design company—Live | Work, Fullerton (2009) pointed out that mixing different stakeholders from different agencies is the foundation for new service success. However, Akama (2009) pointed out that the complexity of the stakeholders and the relationships within the organization are also the problems that affect service design and implementation. At present, there is very limited research on exploring the roles of different stakeholders in co-creation (Rowley, Kupiec-Teahan, & Leeming, 2007). For example, how do stakeholders from different fields get involved and work together? How are different viewpoints of stakeholders balanced? Therefore, this study aims to explore how stakeholders co-create a new service experience and to find out the ways and tools to encourage stakeholders to interact with each other.

METHOD

As noted earlier, this study aims to explore what roles stakeholders play and what problems stakeholders meet in the co-creating service experience process by means of a case study. The case study method is not only a useful and deep approach to understanding the event, but also a way to find out some questions and answers (Yin, 1994). For design domain, Breslin and Buchanan (2008) also pointed out that case studies could establish an effective link between theory and practice. Moreover, Silverman (2006) asserted that an ethnographic approach allows for a deeper understanding of the activities within the organization. Thus, this study adopted the ethnographic approach to obtain deeper insights into how the firm can co-create and deliver service experiences, and to build a detailed description of

the service design project. Secondly, Silverman (2006) argued that the appropriate time of ethnographic observation in an organization usually is between six months and one year. Therefore, the researchers stayed in the company over seven months. Thirdly, employing the notion of service design from Holopainen (2010), the data gathering of active participant observation consists of : 1) meeting and workshops recorded and transcribed, 2) field notes, and 3) artifacts (e.g., memos, photos, and other material). The mentioned data collection consisted of participant observation and interviews. In the process, researchers used audio recorder, camera and note to record service activities, and that allow researchers to understand the participants' conditions and experience. In particular, in addition to know what roles the members played in the service design process, in this study researchers uncovered the principles that could be applied when different stakeholders co-create service experiences.

FIRM PROFILE: LIN'S CERAMICS STUDIO (LCS)

In this study, we presented a case study of *Lin's Ceramics Studio* (hereafter LCS) based on a series of service design (<http://www.aurlia.com.tw/>). LCS was established in 1983, and boasts one of the longest brand histories in ceramics and tea sets. From the beginning, LCS mainly focused on manufacturing products (see Figure 2). The firm doesn't only have great capabilities of product design, production, and quality control; it also has the directly-managed stores in department stores and business districts. Currently, LCS supplies wares to more than 80% of tea-houses in Taiwan, and tries to create different Chinese tea culture experiences and lifestyle to customers through restaurants, directly-managed stores, and exhibitions. For example, in 2010 LCS offered tea services combined with music, dancing and reminiscent setting at the Taiwan Pavilion in Shanghai World Expo. LCS successfully acquainted international visitors with Taiwanese tea culture, and created a deep service experience for them. As mentioned above, the main business of LCS was manufacturing. The firm provided other enterprises with tea products via B2B, and the end users indirectly contacted LCS communities. However, in recent

years, LCS started to move into B2C, and used its own brand to directly service end users. Although LCS's brand position and reputation gradually expanded in Taiwan, China's major cities and western countries, the firm faced serious bottlenecks in its development. For instance, the product-oriented strategy and thinking hardly met customer requirements/needs, the organizational culture was too conservative to create/accept new concepts, and the structure of the organization made it difficult for employees to communicate with network-related stakeholders. Therefore, after 2010 Shanghai World Expo LCS invited its stakeholders to examine the current service, go through service design process, and to co-create new service experiences. LCS wants to outperform in the fierce competition of cultural creative industries through creating unforgettable service experiences.

Figure 2. LCS tea commodities.

LCS CO-CREATING SERVICE EXPERIENCE PROCESS

In order to create new service experiences, the general manager of LCS personally contacted the external service designers and invited relevant stakeholders (see Figure 3, including: customers, salesclerks, designers, marketers, employees, managers and suppliers) to join the service design project. As mentioned earlier, the main phases of the service design process are *discover*, *define*, *develop* and *deliver* (Design Council, 2005), each of which will be described in more detail in the following.

Figure 3. The co-creation framework of service design in LCS.

DISCOVER PHASE

As shown in Figure 3, in order to understand the status of LCS service context and to collect representative and instructive clues, the SDT visited eight typical branches of LCS throughout Taiwan, and then observed and interviewed customers and service providers (see Figure 4). First, SDT disguised themselves as ordinary customers to observe how the salesclerks service customers. In other words, the designer conducted non-participant observations to understand the state of service provided by LCS. At the same time, SDT also observed how people interacted with servicescapes. Second, the design team interviewed customers as well as salesclerks to obtain deeper information. At this point, the data was collected by a group of multi-disciplinary external designers so as to avoid the mindsets of organization members affecting the fairness of data selection. In the data collection process, the professional designers made participants feel respected and recognize the determination of LCS. Besides, in order to have better interaction between researchers and participants, this case used a semi-structured interview. On the one hand, it avoided interviews too casual to obtain valid data. On the other hand, it guided participants to follow the directions and answer questions about the service experience of pre-purchase, during-purchase, and post-purchase. Thirdly, the design team categorized critical dialogue and photo into service experience as

information. Based on that, the design team conducted another interviews with 23 LCS' employees from ten divisions (like salesclerks, designers, marketers, managers). At this phase, the design team found several interesting phenomena described as follows: 1) with regard to *customers*, the service experience was strikingly different depending on the selling areas and age of customers; 2) with regard to *core services*, LCS mainly focused on selling tea commodities. Consequently, the service context cannot meet the different requirements of customers and updates slowly; 3) with regard to *employees*, employees were the key element in LCS' service delivery, because the core value of LCS' products based on their friendly hospitality and professional tea knowledge; 4) as far as *servicescapes* is concerned, there is a tea table in every store, so customers could experience every different test favors and feelings when using different tea sets. 5) The internal interviews revealed that there were serious communication gaps between different divisions and levels. Many employees felt surprising when they read the information that SDT collected, and then gave many comments from their own perspectives.

DEFINE PHASE

Following the previous phase of data collection, the external design team convenes a series of service design workshops for LCS' stakeholders to interact

Figure 4. Customer interviews in LCS.

and co-create together, as shown in Figure 5. The purpose of this phase is to identify service gaps and shape the next opportunities of service experience in the future. At first, the design team divided different stakeholders into several SDTs and engaged participants with design thinking games. Afterward everyone knew they should discuss and express their insight wholeheartedly, and the thoughts of each member are equal and taken seriously. Secondly, these SDTs browsed the same touchpoints pictures and interview dialogue that SDT collected to understand the current service experience and context of LCS. At this time, the design team tried to use images or specific dialogue to help stakeholders to rethink and get empathy. Thirdly, according to their different knowledge background, every SDT grouped service experience clues, established design POVs of service innovation, and proposed possible design concepts by themselves. Finally, the SDT members took turns to vote for design direction and strategy of development in the future. The different roles of stakeholders used different color stickers to vote. Therefore, this approach not only added all votes to decide the specific topic, but also marked different viewpoints of stakeholders through different sticker colors. Moreover, the suggestions from different stakeholders could be a helpful design reference for service development and delivery. At this phase, the focus turned to several service design opportunities, including: 1) to enhance products variety and packaging; 2) to promote memberships benefit within service; 3) to establish deeper relationship between company and the customer and 4) to improve LCS' servicescapes experience through touchpoints.

Firstly, because LCS was based on the manufacturing sector, the participants often focused on tangible products when they talked about the opportunities for service design. In addition, tea culture experiences exist in people's interaction, so the SDTs emphasized more issues about employees' skills, manners, and knowledge. Finally, the participants considered that the servicescapes represent the company's image, and offer a crucial cultural link with customers.

Figure 5. Service design workshops in LCS.

DEVELOP PHASE

In this phase, different stakeholders were also divided into several groups by the external design team. Following defined opportunities and gaps in the previous phase, participants generated multiple concepts and solutions through brainstorming and bodystorming. Interestingly, the design team used a "the rotation of co-creation" approach at this phase, as shown in Figure 6. Every SDT selected one subject for idea creation, and wrote ideas on the post-it and pasted them on newsprint. At the end of the first discussion, each group passed the newsprint to the next SDT and began the second round of discussion. After a few rounds, each SDT got back the original newsprint listing every group's opinions and ideas. At last, they reviewed the advice from different stakeholders. In addition to inspiring more new ideas, the most important objective was to connect the different stakeholders in the design thinking process. Furthermore, they could communicate with cross-departmental, inter-level and multi-disciplinary stakeholders. Finally, the participants could get empathy and systematical thinking from customers

as well as other stakeholders, and the ideas could really be accepted and implemented in the future. Based on the service experience issues raised in the previous phase, the SDTs proposed several concepts. First of all, although the core service and competence of LCS is ceramics and tea sets production, the SDTs realize there should be more cultural and social activities for customers to deliver deeper experience. Simply stated, more engaging services could be offered and created to obtain wider customer base. Therefore, they proposed several new services, such as Cultural Courses, Tea Party and Five-sense Experience of Ceramics. In addition, the SDTs also found that it would be a good idea to empower salesclerks and membership to hold their own activities. Because of their active involvement, new experiences and possibilities would come from new social networks' interaction. Finally, the SDTs created new design concepts for both retail stores and exhibitions based on Five-sense Experience of Ceramics. The SDTs wanted to recruit more designers from diverse fields (e.g. fashion design) to increase brand experience by different sense interface.

Figure 6. The rotation of co-creation in LCS.

DELIVER PHASE

Following the results of the *develop* phase, the design team assisted different SDTs in building a service prototype (see Figure 7). Each SDT created typical personas to shape service concepts (such as Cultural Courses, Tea Party and Five-sense Experience of Ceramics), and presented the service design through prototype, storyboard and drama. Other SDTs assessed the service and gave comments. The SDTs then modify the design or chose to go back to previous phases.

Moreover, SDT integrated the outcomes of the 4Ds phases and drew a new service blueprint for LCS. The service blueprint could allow stakeholders to know how to execute the implementation in the future.

Finally, LCS gathered employees from different departments together for new service deliveries. They confirmed new service is profitable, recognized LCS's capabilities and conditions, and assessed innovation and risk intensity with external SDT. After a series of discussions and evaluations, they could build new service prototypes in a special store and test the prototypes. After the evaluations and modifications, LCS accomplished a plan for the new service deliveries, and planned to launch its new services in the end of 2011.

Figure 7. Service prototype presentation in LCS.

It should be noted that the four phases need to be repeated over and over again and the CEO of LCS as well as stakeholders need to be involved in the overall process. Consequently, when the design team leaves LCS in the future, the organization will be able to co-create service easily. On the other hand, the process and model of co-creation with stakeholders could become a normal rule or an organizational culture.

DISCUSSION

Numerous themes emerged from this case study. The following discussion focuses on main findings that relate specifically to service experiences and co-creation techniques.

THE UNIQUE SERVICE EXPERIENCE OF LCS

In order to create new service experiences, the external design team held a series of interviews and workshops with LCS's different functional employees, service network partners, and end users. This study classified service opportunities and gaps into three categories-core services, employees and servicescapes.

First of all, one of core services of LCS is "professional tea knowledge." Although tea culture originates from traditional lifestyle, tea culture has become a professional and unique ceremony through historical evolution. Furthermore, it has also appeared as an alternative-style tea culture for the young generation. In the *discover* phase, for example, the LCS salesclerks pointed out that "we might need to teach customers about bubble tea as well" in order to improve interaction with customers. In addition, in the *develop* phase, the SDT members also raised some concepts, like "to develop low-order commodities," "to provide oriental culture courses," or "to enhance professional knowledge and culture." Creating these concepts result from the age difference in familiarity estimates. For the tea cultural creative services, LCS should not only provide existing customers with professional core service, but also infuse tea knowledge into customers by different interfaces or create new approaches to integrate tea with new lifestyles. As a result, LSC would attract wider customer bases that are unfamiliar with tea or younger people, and then has a opportunity to break the limitation of customer age from 45 and 65.

Secondly, the main function offered by *employees* aims at a high level "interactive relationship." In the *discover* phase, the design teams found some issues, for example, the characteristic of regular customers are fond of "drinking tea and sharing;" salesclerks need to "understand customer preferences though conversation." In the *develop* phase, the members pointed out that the salesclerks plays a crucial role as "a medium for knowledge delivery and interaction." The rich emotional experience of tea culture is created around human touch and caring; furthermore, the mentioned experiences need to be co-created by customers and enterprises.

Thirdly, "consistent experience" is necessary for *servicescapes*. In the *discover* phase, the design

team found that the current servicescapes are limited to exhibitions and sales environment, route, and space restrictions, so the servicescapes in stores are often messy and inconsistent. Therefore, in the *develop* phase, many participants proposed "to display by topic" and "to set up the service experience standard of five senses," to create a brand image and the overall service experience. In summary, these suggestions of service experiences can be treated as principles of cultural creative service, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. New service experiences of LCS.

THE CRITICAL FACTORS IN CO-CREATION

After completion of the four phases of LCS co-creation, there are five main findings in this study. First of all, strong management support and full participation from the CEO is critical. Since the CEO brings all of the senior managers to join for all the phases, they highly motivate the members of the organization who participate in the project; besides, they successfully support stakeholders (such as customers and suppliers) to co-create LCS' service together and effectively build a coherent consideration of different objectives. Secondly, involvement of salesclerks is also very crucial. Salesclerks did not only provide some important information, but were also responsible for the smooth delivery of the service experience in the future (Fullerton, 2009). In this study, the salesclerks always played an active role. They assessed services from the customer's viewpoint. Thirdly, involvement and observations from a third party (such as a SDT) provided balanced, creative and attractive ways to encourage co-creation between different stakeholders. The third party

explored service gaps impartially, and was a good medium/interface to balance and encourage all participants. Because of their professional and interdisciplinary background, the third party provided different insights in service design phases and assisted LCS in exploring things in new ways. Fourthly, visualization tools employed in the service design project could be treated as key elements in enhancing the co-creation of service experience. Because participants came from diverse domains, the professional terminology and mindset prevented them from understanding and communicating with others; moreover, service is intangible and abstract. Segelström (2009) claims that visualizations induce creative thinking in the practice of service design. For example, in this case a single image, continuous film and service prototypes were used to visualize concepts, and helped SDTs to group and reframe insights. Furthermore, the SDT would use different color of stickers to vote. This kind of color system did promote people's capability of visual selection, and sped up the efficiency of service co-creation. Lastly, as we know, complex stakeholder involvement and LCS' culture brought many challenges in the service design process. Therefore, this case study employed "the rotation of co-creation" as a critical method to guide stakeholders to work and get empathy together. To sum up, the co-creation can help all stakeholders to understand what service values should be in the service value chain. Moreover, it can create a unique and holistic service experience based on these values.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

To sum up, the findings of this study have three main implications. First, as for LCS, the introductions of co-creation service design not only generate new service experiences, but also allow the stakeholders from different departments to understand in depth the service experience on both the enterprises and customer sides. Secondly, for the cultural creative industry, the findings of this case study provide a feasible framework of service co-creating for the future studies and offer service experience elements and implements for the cultural creative industry. Thirdly, as for the implementation of co-creation, the results of this case study demonstrate the appropriate roles of the designers could play in

different phases and the critical methods and tools of co-creation.

However, it is evident that much needs to be elaborated and further evaluated. Since co-creation is a new framework of dynamic relationship between organization and customers (Pralhad & Ramaswamy, 2004), it is important for a firm to view service design as an ongoing program rather than a one-shot activity, especially in a dynamic and increasingly competitive marketplace. Finally, having acknowledged the limitation of time, this study only analyzed a single case. To consider the different backgrounds of the individual cases, future studies should discuss more cases in order to establish a more rigorous research framework.

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